

Table 1 Incomplete statistics of hydrogen-related policies released by China in 2025

Month	National	Local	Total
Jan. ¹	5	19	24
Feb. ²	6	18	24
Mar. ³	3	29	32
Apr. ⁴	8	29	37
May ⁵	5	28	33
Jun. ⁶	8	44	52
Jul. ⁷	6	30	36
Aug. ⁸	2	32	34
Sept. ⁹	11	22	33
Oct. ¹⁰	8	21	29
Nov. ¹¹	10	29	39
Dec. ¹²	11	35	46
			419

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